

WORDFORMATION'S WAYS

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Annotation: The shortening of words means substituting a part for a whole, part of the word is taken away and used for the whole. For example, demo (demonstration), dub (double), vac (vacuum cleaner), doc (doctor), fig (figure), Mrs (missis). A shortened word is in some way different from its prototype in usage. The shortened word and its full form have the same lexical meaning but differ only in stylistic reference.

Key words: Graphical abbreviations, stylistic reference, syllables of a word, splinter, soundinterchange,

Shortened words are structurally simple words "and in most cases have the same lexical meaning as the longer words from which they are derived. Shortening is not a derivational process because there are no structural patterns after which new shortened words could be built therefore we can't say that shortening is a derivational wordformation.

Abbreviations consist of the first letters of a word group or a compound word (U.K.CHH, USA, BBC, NATO) or the component of a two member word group H (hydrogin)— bomb, V. —Day — Victory Day) is shortened. The last one is not changed. [1,2,3,4,5]

Clipping consists in the cutting off of one or several syllables of a word. In many cases the stressed syllables are preserved. For example. Sis. (sister), Jap

(Japanese), doc (doctor), phone (telephone), lab (laboratory). Clipping is classified into the following types depending on which part of the word is clipped: 1) Words that have been shortened at the end: For example, ad (advertisement), lab (laboratory), Jap (Japanese), doc (doctor), sis (sister), vac (vacuum cleaner) ;2) Words that have been shortened at the beginning: ear, car (motor-car), phone (telephone), van (caravan), cast (broadcast); 3) Words in which syllables have been omitted from the middle the so called syncope, For example, maths (mathematics), specs (spectacles); 4) Words that have been shortened at the beginning and at the end: For example, flu (influenza), tec (detective), frig (refrigerator). [4,5,6,]

Clippings and abbreviations have some peculiarities as simple words. They take the plural endings and that of the possessive case. They take grammatical inflexions, For example, exams, docs, cars, doc's they are used with articles: the USA , a lab, a vac, a doc, etc.

They may take derivational affixes: M. P-ess hanky (from handkerchief), unkie (from uncle).Clippings do not always coincide in meaning with the original word. For : "doc" and "doctor" have the meaning one who practises medicine, but Tutor is also the highest degree given by a university to a scholar or scientist and a person who has received such a degree whereas doc is not used with these meanings.

Among abbreviations there are homonyms. One and the same sound and graphical complex may be different words. For example, vac-vacation; vac-vacuum cleaner; prep-preparation; prep-preparatory school. In abbreviations we stress each letter. For example. TUC ['ti:'ju:'si:]—Trade Union Congress. If

they are pronounced in accordance with the rules of phonetics we stress the first syllable.

For example, NATO t'neitou], UNO ['ju:nou] BBC — British Broadcasting Corporation, Cent—Centigrade. AP—Associated Press, GPO—General Post Office, USA—United States of America, UNESCO—United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization, USAF—United States Air Force, WFDY—World Federation of Democratic Youth, WFTU—World Federation of Trade Unions, SEATO—South-East Asia Treaty Organization, UK—United Kingdom, NAS—National Academy of Sciences, NY—New York, NZ—New Zealand, MD—Doctor of Medicine, FAP—First Aid Post. [5,6,7,8,9]

sub (submarine), surg (surgeon), Sept (September), Serg (sergeant), esp (especially), capt (captain), lat (latitude), Wash (Washington), Wed (Wednesday), usu (usually), pref (preface), prof (professor), prox (proximo), mos (months), quot (quotation), revs (revolutions), Russ (Russian), sat (Saturday), vol (volume), rep (representative), suppl (supplement).

In the process of communication words and word-groups can be shortened. The causes of shortening can be linguistic and extra-linguistic. By extra-linguistic causes changes in the life of people are meant. In Modern English many new abbreviations, acronyms , initials, blends are formed because the tempo of life is increasing and it becomes necessary to give more and more information in the shortest possible time.

There are also linguistic causes of abbreviating words and word-groups, such as the demand of rhythm, which is satisfied in English by monosyllabic words. When borrowings from other languages are assimilated in English they are shortened. Here we have modification of form on the basis of analogy, For

example the Latin borrowing «fanaticns» is shortened to «fan» on the analogy with native words: man, pan, tan etc. [8,9,10,11,12]

There are two main types of shortenings : graphical and lexical. Graphical abbreviations are the result of shortening of words and word-groups only in written speech while orally the corresponding full forms are used. They are used for the economy of space and effort in writing. The oldest group of graphical abbreviations in English is of Latin origin. In Russian and Uzbek this type of abbreviation is not typical. In these abbreviations in the spelling Latin words are shortened, while orally the corresponding English equivalents are pronounced in the full form, For example. (Latin *exempli gratia*), a.m. - in the morning (*ante meridiem*), No - number (*numero*), p. a. - a year (*per annum*), d - penny (*dinarius*). pound (*libra*), i. e. - that is (*id est*) etc.

Some graphical abbreviations of Latin origin have different English equivalents in different contexts, For example, p.m. can be pronounced «in the afternoon» (*post meridiem*) and «after death» (*post mortem*).

There are also graphical abbreviations of native origin, where in the spelling we have abbreviations of words and word-groups of the corresponding English equivalents in the full form. We have several semantic groups of them.

In some cases the translation of initialisms is next to impossible without using special dictionaries. Initialisms are denoted in different ways. Very often they are expressed in the way they are pronounced in the language of their origin, For example. ANZUS (Australia , New Zealand , United States) SALT (Strategic Arms Limitation Talks). In Russian as (договор об ограничении стратегических вооружений).

Abbreviation of words consists in clipping a part of a word. As a result we get a new lexical unit where either the lexical meaning or the style is different from the full form of the word. In such cases as «fantasy» and «fancy», «fence» and «defencey» we have different lexical meanings. In such cases as «laboratory!» and «lab», we have different styles. [1,2,3,4,5,6]

Abbreviation does not change the part-of-speech meaning, as we have it in the case of conversion or affixation, it produces words belonging to the same part of speech as the primary word, For example, prof is a noun and professor is also a noun. Mostly nouns undergo abbreviation, but we can also meet abbreviation of verbs, such as to rev from to revolve, to tab from to tabulate etc. But mostly abbreviated forms of verbs are formed by means of conversion from abbreviated nouns, For example, to taxi, to vac etc. Adjectives can be abbreviated but they are mostly used in school slang and are combined with suffixation, For example. comfy, dilly, mizzy etc. As a rule pronouns, numerals, interjections, conjunctions are not abbreviated. The exceptions are: fif (fifteen), teen-ager, in one's teens (apheresis from numerals from 13 to 19).

Lexical abbreviations are classified according to the part of the word which is clipped. Mostly the end of the word is clipped, because the beginning of the word in most cases is the root and expresses the lexical meaning of the word. This type of abbreviation is called apocope.

Here we can mention a group of words ending in «o», such as disco (dicotheque), expo (exposition), intro (introduction) and many others. On the analogy with these words there developed in Modern English a number of words where «o» is added as a kind of a suffix to the shortened form of the word, For example. combo (combination) to, - Afro (African). In other cases the

beginning of the word is clipped. In such cases we have apheresis, For example, chute (Parachute), varsity (university), copter (helicopter), those (enthusiasm) etc.

Sometimes the middle of the word is clipped, For example, market (market), fanzine (fan magazine), maths (mathematics). Such abbreviations are called syncope. Sometimes we have a combination of syncope with apheresis, when the beginning and the end of the word are clipped, For example, tec (detective), van (vanguard) etc. [6,7,8,9,10,11,12]

Sometimes shortening influences the spelling of the word, For example, «cil» can be substituted by «k» before «e» to preserve pronunciation, For example, mike (microphone), Coke (Coca-Cola) etc. The same rule is observed in the following cases: fax (facsimile), teck (technical college), trunk (tranquilizer) etc. The final consonants in the shortened forms are substituted by letters characteristic of native English words.

In the second half of the twentieth century the English wordbuilding system was enriched by creating so-called splinters which scientists include in the affixation stock of the Modern English wordbuilding system. Splinters are the result of clipping the end or the beginning of a word and producing a number of new words on the analogy with the primary word-group. For example, there are many words formed with the help of the splinter mini- (apocope produced by clipping the word «miniature»), such as «miniplane», «minijet», «minicyde», «minicar», «miniradio» and many others. All of these words denote objects of smaller than normal dimensions. On the analogy with «mini-» there appeared the splinter «maxi-» (apocope produced by clipping the

word «maximum»), such words as «maxi-series», «maxi sculpture», «maxi-taxi» and many others appeared in the language.

When European economic community was organized quite a number of neologisms with the splinter Euro- (apocopy produced by clipping the word «European») were coined, such as: «Euratom» «Eurocard», «Euromarket» «Europlug», «Eurotunnel» and many others. These splinters are treated sometime as prefixes in Modern English.

There are also splinters which are formed by means of apheresis, that is clipping the beginning of a word. The origin of such splinters can be variable, for example, the splinter «burger» appeared in English as the result of clipping the German borrowing «Hamburger» where the morphological structure was the stem «Hamburg» and the suffix -er. However in English the beginning of the word «Hamburger» was associated with the English word «ham», and the end of the word «burger» got the meaning «a bun cut into two parts». On the analogy with the word «hamburger» quite a number of new words were coined, such as «baconburger», «beefburger», «cheeseburger», «fishburger» etc.

The splinter «cade» developed by clipping the beginning of the word «cavalcade» which is of Latin origin. In Latin the verb with the meaning «to ride on horses» is «cabalicare» and by means of the inflexion -ata the corresponding Participle is formed. [8,9,10,11,12]

So the element «cade» is a combination of the final letter of the stem and the -n flexion. The splinter «cade» serves to form nouns with the meaning «connected with the procession of vehicles denoted by the first component»), For example. («aircade» - «a group of airplanes accompanying the plane of a

VIP» , «autocade» . «a group of automobiles escorting the automobile of a VIP», «musicade» -«an orchestra participating in a procession”.

In the seventieths of the twentieth century there was a political scandal in the hotel «Watergate» where the Democratic Party of the USA had its pre-election headquarters. Republicans managed to install bugs there and when they were discovered there was a scandal and the ruling American government had to resign. The name «Watergate» acquired the meaning «a political scandal», «corruption». On the analogy with this word quite a number of other words were formed by using the splinter «gate» (apheresis of the word «Watergate»), such as: «Irangate», «Westlandgate», «shuttlegate», «milliongate» etc. The splinter «gate» is added mainly to Proper names: names of people with whom the scandal is connected or a geographical name denoting the place where the scandal occurred. The splinter «mobile» was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «automobile» and is used to denote special types of automobiles, such as: «artmobile», «bookmobile», «snowmobile», «tourmobile» etc. [6,7,8,9,10]

The splinter «napper» was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «kidnappery) and is used to denote different types of crimesters, such as : «busnapper», «babynapper», «dognapper» etc. From such nouns the corresponding verbs are formed by means of backformation, For example. «to busnap», «to babynap», «to dognap».

The splinter «omat» was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «automat» (a cafe in which meals are provided in slot-machines). The meaning «self-service» is used in such words as «laundromat», «cashomat» etc.

Another splinter «eten'a» with the meaning «self-service» was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «cafeteria». By means of the splinter «eteria» the following words were formed: «groceteria», «booketeria», «booteteria» and many others. [8,9,10,11,12]

The splinter «quake» is used to form new words with the meaning of «shaking», «agitation». This splinter was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «earthquake». The following words were formed with the help of this splinter: «Marsquake», «Moonquake», «youthquake» etc.

The splinter «rama(ama)» is a clipping of the word «panorama» of Greek origin where «pan» means «all» and «horama» means «view». In Modern English the meaning «view» was lost and the splinter «rama» is used in advertisements to denote objects of supreme quality, for example «autorama» means «exhibition- sale of expensive cars», «trouserama» means «sale of trousers of supreme quality») etc.

The splinter «scape» is a clipping of the word «landscape» and it is used to form words denoting different types of landscapes, such as: «moonscape», «streetscape», «townscape», «seascape» etc. Another case of splinters is «tel» which is the result of clipping the beginning of the word «hotely». It serves to form words denoting different types of hotels, such as: «motel» (motor-car hotel) «boatel» (boat hotel), «floatel» (a hotel on water, floating), «airtel» (airport hotel etc. [5,10,11,12]

The splinter «theque» is the result of clipping the beginning of the word «apothecary» of Greek origin which means in Greek «a store house». In Russian words: «Купитека», «Горьковская» the element «Тека» corresponding to the English «theque» preserves the meaning of storing something which is

expressed by the first component of the word. In English the splinter «theque» is used to denote a place for dancing, such as: «discotheque», «jazzotheque»)).

The splinter «thon» is the result of clipping the beginning of the word «marathon». «Marathon» primarily was the name of a battle-field in Greece, forty miles from Athens, where there was a battle between the Greek and the Persian. When the Greek won a victory a Greek runner was sent to Athens to tell people about the victory. Later on the word « Marathon » was used to denote long-distance competitions in running. The splinter «thon(athon)» denotes «something continuing for a long time», competition in endurance)) For example, «dancathon», «telethon», «speakathon», «readathon», «walkathon», «moviethon», «swimathon», «talkathon», «swearthon» etc.

Splinters can be the result of clipping adjectives or substantivized adjectives. The splinter «aholic» (holic) was formed by clipping the beginning of the word «alcoholic» of Arabian origin where «al» denoted «the», «koh'l» - «powder for staining lids». The splinter «(a)holic» means «infatuated by the object expressed by the stem of the word», For ex«/Mp/e.«bookaholic», «computerholic», «coffeeholic», «cheesaholic», «workaholic» and many others.

The splinter «genic» formed by clipping the beginning of the word «photogenic» denotes the notion «suitable for something denoted by the stem», For example.«a\ergemc», «cardiogenic», «mediagenic», «telegenic» etc.

As far as verbs are concerned it is not typical of them to be clipped that is why there is only one splinter to be used for forming new verbs in this way. It is the splinter «cast» formed by clipping the beginning of the verb «broadcast». This splinter was used to form the verbs «telecast» and «abroadcast».

Splinters can be called pseudomorphemes because they are neither roots nor affixes, they are more or less artificial. In English there are words which consist of two splinters. For example «telethon», therefore it is more logical to call words with splinters in their structure ((compound-shortened words consisting of two clippings of words». [5,6,7,8,9]

Splinters have only one function in English: they serve to change the lexical meaning of the same part of speech, whereas prefixes and suffixes can also change (the part-of-speech meaning). For example the prefix «en-» and its allomorph «em-» can form verbs from noun and adjective stems («embody», «enable», «endanger») «be-» can form verbs from noun and adjective stems («becloud», «benumb») «-» can form noun and adjective stems («becloud», «benumb»), «post-» and «pre-» can form adjectives from noun stems («pre-election campaign», «post-war events»)

The main function of suffixes is to form one part of speech from another part of speech, For example. «-er», «-ing», «-ment» form nouns from verbal stems («teacher», «dancing», «movement»), «-ness», «-ity» are used to form nouns from adjective stems («clannishness», «marginality»).

Sound interchange is an alternation in the phonetic composition of the root, for example, food (n) —feed (v), speak (v)— speech (n), strong (adj) — strength (n). Sound interchange may be considered as a way of forming words only diachronically because in Modern English we can't find a single word which can be formed by changing the root-vowel of a word or by shifting the place of the stress. Sound interchange is non-productive.

Sound interchange may be divided into vowel interchange and consonant interchange. For example fill—to fill, food—to feed, blood—to bleed,

stronger— strength. Here we have vowel interchange and by means of vowel interchange we can distinguish different parts of speech. There are some examples of consonant interchange: advice—to advise, speak—speech, break—breach, defence—defend, offence— offend.

The scientist argue that sound interchange is the way of word-building when some sounds are changed to form a new word. It is non-productive in Modern English, it was productive in Old English and can be met in other Indo-European languages.

The causes of sound interchange can be different. It can be the result of Ancient Ablaut which cannot be explained by the phonetic laws during the period of the language development known to scientists., For example to strike - stroke, to sing - song etc. It can be also the result of Ancient Umlaut or vowel mutation which is the result of palatalizing the root vowel because of the front vowel in the syllable coming after the root (regressive assimilation), For example hot - to heat (hotian), blood - to bleed (blodian) etc. In many cases we have vowel and consonant interchange. In nouns we have voiceless consonants and in verbs we have corresponding voiced consonants because in Old English these consonants in nouns were at the end of the word and in verbs in the intervocal position, For example bath - to bathe, life - to live, breath - to breathe etc.

Stress interchange can be mostly met in verbs and nouns of Romanic origin : nouns have the stress on the first syllable and verbs on the last syllable, For example. 'accent - to accent. This phenomenon is explained in the following way: trench verbs and nouns had different structure when they were borrowed into English, verbs had one syllable more than the corresponding nouns. When

these borrowings were assimilated in English the stress in them was shifted to the previous syllable (the second from the end).

Later on the last unstressed syllable in verbs borrowed from French was dropped (the same as in native verbs) and after that the stress in verbs was on the last syllable while in nouns it was on the first syllable. As a result of it we have such pairs in English as : to con"flikt- "conflict, to ex'port -'export, to ex'traet - "extract etc. As a result of stress interchange we have also vowel interchange i n such words because vowels are pronounced differently in stressed and unstressed positions. [9,10,11,12]

It is the way of word-building when a word is formed by dropping the final morpheme to form a new word. It is opposite to suffixation, that is why it is called backformation. At first it appeared in the language as a result of misunderstanding the structure of a borrowed word. Prof. Yartseva 1 explains this mistake by the influence of the whole system of the language on separate words. For example, it is typical of English to form nouns denoting the agent of the action by adding the suffix -er to a verb stem (speak-speaker). So when the French word «beggar» was borrowed into English the final syllable «ar» was pronounced in the same way as the English -er and Englishmen formed the verb «to beg» by dropping the end of the noun. Other examples of backformation are : to accreditate (from accreditation), to bach (from bachelor), to collocate (from collocation), to enthuse (from enthusiasm), to compute (from computer), to emote (from emotion) to reminisce (from reminiscence), to televise (from television) etc.

As we can notice in cases of backformation the part-of-speech meaning of the primary word is changed, verbs are formed from nouns. Thus, The term

«back-Formation” has a diachronic relevance (historical meaning). For example. The nouns beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter are very much like the nouns actor, painter, teacher, which have the suffixes -er, -or. On the analogy of the derivatives teacher, speaker, reader the words beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter etc. synchronically are derived from to beg, to butle, to cob, to typewrite, because we do not feel any difference between the relationship «speak—speaker» and «beg— beggar» - But if we study their origin we see «butle» was derived from «butler».

So backformation «denotes the derivation of new words by subtracting a real or supposed affix from existing words through misinterpretation of their structure.

Backformation is in fact an example of analogy, the speaker knows pairs like rob /robber and drink/ drinker and when he hears the word «beggar» he makes it conform to the pattern by inventing a form «beg». Another well-known historical example of back-formation in English is the verb «to sidele», from the adverb«sideling».

Blending is the formation of a new word by a connection of parts of two words to form one word.

For example. The noun «smog» is composed of the parts of nouns «smoke» and «fog» (sm (oke+f) og. The result of blending is an unanalysable simple word. We do not analyse the blended words (sm+og) because their parts can't be called morphemes .For example. clash- clap'crash; flush-flash H-blush,l slanguage=slang+language, brunch- breakfast+lunch, smare-smoke+haze, seadrome=-sea+airdrome). There are many blends in the terminological

vocabulary. For example, racon-radar+beacon, transceiver-transmitter+receiver.

Blending can be considered ... as the method of merging (connecting) parts of words into one new word as when «sm+oke» and «fog» derived from «smog».

Thus, blending is compounding by means of curtailed (shortened) words. However, the clusters «sm» and «og» were morphemes only for the individual speaker who blended them while in terms of the linguistic system as recognized by the community, there are not signs at all. Blending, therefore, has no grammatical, but a stylistic status. The result of blending is ... an unanalysable, simple word, not a motivated syntagma. (H.Marchand) [4,5,6,7,8]

Blends are also words formed from a word-group or two synonyms. In blends two ways of word-building are combined : abbreviation and composition. To form a blend we clip the end of the first component (apocope) and the beginning of the second component (apheresis). As a result we have a compound-shortened word. One of the first blends in English was the word «smog» from two synonyms : smoke and fog which means smoke mixed with fog. From the first component the beginning is taken, from the second one the end, «o» is common for both of them.

Blends formed from two synonyms are: slanguage, to hustle, gasohol etc. Mostly blends are formed from a word-group, such as : acromania (acronym mania), cinemadict (cinema adict), chunnel (channel, canal), dramedy (drama comedy), detectifiction (detective fiction), faction (fact fiction) (fiction based on real facts), informecial (information commercial), Medicare (medical care),

magalog (magazine catalogue) slimnastics (slimming gymnastics), sociolite (social elite), slanguist (slang linguist) etc.

RESOURCES

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